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on / &w k t r \$ t p m r sm; u ll y ll h & t & c f cm; j c i f? z 0 p o y l t & c f cm; j c i f E S h t c 0 t c s t & c f cm; j c i f
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aon t s u p u m; v l r sm - &w l o b i l t a j c t a e? { u y ll t j z n i c ll y ll p ll o y a p E S u l
a w m i l w l v e l l y ' r m l u m q l l y l v l v p l v e l l o E h w p l v e l l , E l m; p l u m /

edgef

y k h c w r s t p j y l c h o m j r e f m p m a y o n i a c w f t q u q u i z 0 z 0 w l w u l v m c l y g o n /
y k h c w l o n i a u s m u p m v f r l l o n h a c w j z p j y 0 y i f, a c w r p i u A s m v u f r s m; y l y i p 0 h
x e f u m; v m c l y g o n / &w l u A s m o n i u A s m v u f r y l y i p 0 h a y : x e f o n h y i f, a c w r s o n f
, a e l a c w f t x d a y : x e f v s u & h o m o u i w r f t & s h q l l u A s m t r \$ t p m r sm; j z p l y g o n / &w k
u A s m \ t p o n i p w & * A v t r w l l u d u a r ; a v 0 u f i a y g u l q & m a w m l u a j z l u m; a o m
a r ; a j z & w k v p p l y i j z p o n /] & w l l p w i f a y : x e f p u] y s l l } [l o m a c : a 0 : o h E e f x m; o n /
o l l a o m] & w l l o n i] y s l l } E S h r w a y / &w l u A s m o n i y ll h & t u e l l t o w ? u A s m t q l c s
p m v l l a & t u e l l t o w ? t q l c s p u m; v l l o w r s v f c s u r s m; E S h p n i p e p l l u 0 a o m u A s m
w p r s j z p o n / x b ll p n i p e p l l u 0 i o u i w r f & s h a o m u A s m v p r s t \ * P & n l u l l
a z m x k w l v h o m q E j z i h p p m w r f u l l j y l p c l y g o n /

ohwoe&n&G tsuESh t o llylenf

j r e f m p m a y o n i l l f w 0 f a c w f t q u q u i r j y w a y : x 0 u t c h o m u A s m v p r s t \
t " y 0 h, z 0 l q l t s u r s m; E S h t r \$ t p m r sm; c f cm; y l v l l u l l a v l v m a z m x k w l v h o m & n & G f c u f
j z p l y g o n / &w l u A s m \ z 0 l q l t s u r s m; u ll u s r f t o 0 o b \ t q l t r e f r s m; E S h a v l v m w i f y
x m; j y 0 &w l u A s m t r \$ t p m r sm; u ll t a x m u f t x m; t u l t u m; r s m; E S h & 0 a z 0 a v l v m w i f y x m; y g
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x||a||umi|&w|k|t|t|p|;c|&m|w||y|f y|g|o|i|a|om|ty||ft|&v|n|fa|umi|? t|q||c|s|p|v|| ta|&t|w|u|u|| v|u||f|v|n|fa|umi|? t|q||c|s|y'|w|g|y|g|om tu|&p|um;v||u||v|u||f| v|n|fa|umi|? ty||ft|w||t|&|n|ft|v|u||f trn| to|o|o|y|i|v|n|fa|umi| c|j|c|m;x|m;a||umi|f aw|&y|gon/

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p|p|m|v|r|f|w||f &w|a|O|g|[m|&E|h &w|u|A|sm|t|t|p|m; c|j|c|m;y||r|m;u|| av|h|m|w|i|y x|m;y|gon/ &w|u|A|sm|o|n|i|y|f, acw|f|p|w|i|f|y|:ay|g|u|o|n|i|q|h|o|m|v|n|f| t|i|f|O|acw|f|p|i x|i|x|i|f|y|:ay|: r|m;r|m;p|m;p|m; aw|&a|om u|A|sm|v|p|r|t|j|z|p|o|n/ &w|u|A|sm|E|h|y|w|b|u|f| z|G|q|l|t|s|u|f|t|o|o|w||f &w|k [h|o|m|a|O|g|[m|&o|n|i|y|g|v|b|m|o|m|p|u|m;r|s|q|i|f|o|u|b|o|n|f|m|r|u j|r|e|r|m|p|u|m; p|p|p|v|n|f|&||u||m|i|f|aw|&|o|n/ t|r|m;p|k|v|h|a|om z|G|q|l|t|s|u|f|f|n| &w|k|[l|o|n|i|]|o|b|i|}]|t|c|r|f|t|e|m;}]]|t|a|j|c|t|a|e|}]|h|o|m|t|e|u|y|i|j|z|p|o|n/ u|A|sm|z|p|e|p|r|f|n| av;v|k|p|y|f u|A|sm|i|j|z|p|o|n/ o|a|o|m|y|s|? &u|e|? a|r|m|u|e|f|w|E|h|u|f|y|m;|o|n|r|f|n| t|q||c|s|p|v|| ta|&t|w|u|f|u|e|l|o|w|t|s|u|f|c|i|f|j|z|p|o|n/ &w|k t|c|p|m|v|a|&|o|n|i|c|E|p|v|h|r|s|o|h|q, h|g;v|k| t|x|d|&|y|o|n/ x|j|c|m;|o|n|r|f|n|]|r|} *P|e|f| ta|&t|w|u|f|r|m;|o|m|j|z|p|a||u||m|i|f| aw|&|o|n/ &w|l|o|n|i|y|g|o|i|a|om| ty||ft|a|&t|w|u|u|b|m|r|u| y|g|o|i|a|om|y'| ta|&t|w|u|u|v|n|f| u|e|l|o|w|f x|m;y|gon/ &w|k|w|p|y||f|u|| (108)y'|x|u|y|| z|l|a|v|r|&||u||m|i|f| aw|&|o|n/ o|a|o|m|f| w|p|y||ft|w||f| y'|u|e|l|o|w|t|s|u|f|&|y|/ x||a||u||m|i|h| w|p|y||E|h|w|p|y||f|t|&|n|ft|w|l|r|n|E|h|f| a||u||m|i|f|v|n|f| aw|&y|gon/ w|p|y||E|h|w|p|y||f|t|&|n|ft|w|l|u|j|c|m;|c|s|u|f|t|&v|n|f| &w|k|t|r|t| t|p|m; c|j|c|m;x|m;y|gon/ p|o|l|i|z|i|h|&w|u|A|sm|o|n|i|y||f|a|&r|r|m;|a|o|m|v|n|f| p|n|f|p|e|p|l|u|a|o|m u|A|sm|v|p|r|t|j|z|p|a||u||m|i|f| av|h|m|a|v|&|y|gon/

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